

Cultural Congruity and the Perception towards The College Environment by the Undergraduate International Students

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Abstract

The study assessed the cultural congruity and the perception towards the college environment by the international students. The researchers explored this study as a basis for a student development program by utilizing well developed and tested instruments such as Cultural Congruity Scale and the University Environment Scale. This research study used descriptive-correlational design. The data gathered from the 82 respondents were treated using the Pearson r Product Moment for Coefficient of Correlation. The study reveals that the undergraduate international students have high level of perception towards cultural congruity and the university environment. However, there is no significant relationship between the scores of the perception in cultural congruity and the university environment.

Keywords: Cultural Congruity. Undergraduate International Students. Environment.

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Introduction

Throughout the years the number of students enrolling to a foreign country has grown significantly. As a matter of fact, the Philippine Bureau of Immigration Statistics has reported about the tremendous number of international students coming to the country registered at 26,000 in 2011 to more than 61,000 in 2012.

This study was conducted to answer questions pertaining to how the International students perceived the institution. Does the institution provide the requirements to optimize the learning experience needed by the International students? Is the college doing a good job in addressing the needs of the students? Is the college doing its part in enabling students to fit properly with their peers in school? Are there programs in place to make the environment wholesome? Are the college programs, curriculum, faculty, student body and alumni network doing their part in ensuring that these students are not only intellectually progressing, but also being socio-culturally equipped to take on a contributory role to society once they leave the gates of the academe? To answer these questions, the study gathered data concerning the Cultural Congruity (factor in which most international students in each institution find from the nationals and how they find the Institution's Environment appropriate for them, i.e. Can they practice their own beliefs? Do what they usually do at home, and express their ideas to everyone around them, which includes teachers and classmates.) While the University Environment (refers to the atmosphere or environment of the institution) as perceived by the enrolled students of the college. The study is anchored with Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory also known as the cultural-historical psychology theory, which encompassed numerous empirical studies and provided a comprehensive theoretical description of sociocultural nature of learning. In particular, this study's theoretical foundation incorporated Vygotsky's, who postulated that culture determines not only what is learned but also how it is learned. In the context of this research, this implies that students who travel abroad to study bring with them a wealth of cultural resources and expectations culturally predetermined interaction patterns and learning style preferences that shape their behavior in the new environment. After gathering the answers to these questions, the researchers designed the Bridges to Learn, Empower and Nurture Diversity of Students (BLENDS) Program, a three - year student development program focusing on the improvement of the cultural congruity and the perception of the university environment by the International students for policy recommendation to the management of the college.

Methodology

This study aimed to determine the perception of the International students at St. Dominic College of Asia in terms of Cultural Congruity and University Environment.

This study used the descriptive correlational design to assess the relationship between and among two or more variables (Stangor, 2011). Descriptive Correlational is a type of research that creates a snapshot of the current state of the variables and assesses the relationship between two or more variables involved (University of Minnesota, n.d.).

This research has involved undergraduate international students of St. Dominic College of Asia enrolled in Academic Year 2018 – 2019. This involved 82 respondents or 78% of the total population of the International students at St. Dominic College of Asia. The instruments used in data gathering of this study are the Cultural Congruity Scale (CCS) is a 13-item instrument that was designed to measure Chicano/a students' sense of cultural congruity or cultural fit within the college environment and the University Environment Scale (UES) a 14-item designed to measure university students' perceptions of the university environment. It was developed specifically to identify minority students' perceptions. Both instruments were authored by Alberta M. Gloria and Sharon E. Robinsons – Kurpios.

Results from the scales were statistically treated using the Pearson r Product Moment for Coefficient of Correlation to measure how strong the relationship of two variables.

Results and Discussion

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
MALE	59	71.95
FEMALE	19	23.17
UNSPECIFIED	4	4.88
Total	82	100%

The data reveal that 71.95% of the participants are males, while 19 23.17% are females. However, four of the respondents or 4.88% did not specify their gender.

Table 1.2 Profile of Respondents according to Nationality

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
NIGERIAN	70	85.37
AMERICAN	2	2.44
ITALIAN AMERICAN	1	1.22
JAPANESE	1	1.22
NO ANSWER	8	9.75
Total	82	100%

The profile of the respondents indicate according to nationality of which out of 82 participants, 70 respondents or 85% of the sampled participants are Nigerians. This is the nationality of most of the foreign students at SDCA. Only two 2 are Americans, and there is only one Italian-American and one Japanese which both represent 1%. However, eight of the respondents or 9.75% did not specify their nationality.

Table 1.3 Result of the Cultural Congruity Scale

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CCS1	82	1.00	7.00	3.8049	2.13980
CCS2	82	1.00	7.00	3.4878	1.83413
CCS3	82	1.00	8.00	3.7195	2.14461
CCS4	82	1.00	7.00	3.8049	2.34883
CCS5	82	1.00	7.00	4.2561	2.19883
CCS6	82	1.00	7.00	4.4512	2.19513
CCS7	82	1.00	7.00	4.0732	2.25958
CCS8	82	1.00	7.00	5.2805	1.77273
CCS9	82	1.00	7.00	3.6829	2.07797
CCS10	82	1.00	7.00	4.0122	2.32269
CCS11	82	1.00	7.00	5.0366	1.87541
CCS12	82	1.00	7.00	5.0000	1.80534
CCS13	82	1.00	7.00	5.2561	1.87123
CCSs-core	82	33.00	85.00	55.8659	11.03615

The average score of each item in the cultural congruity scale and the total mean score which is 55.8659. This score translates to an average level of perceived cultural congruity by the International students. Thus, the international students state that there is an average congruence between the culture they have experienced at home and the culture they are experiencing at SDCA.

Table 1.4 The University Environment Scale

	N	Mini- mum	Maxi- mum	Mean	Std. De- viation
UES1	82	1.00	7.00	4.3415	1.86732
UES2	82	1.00	7.00	5.1463	2.02528
UES3	82	1.00	7.00	5.0854	1.86720
UES4	82	1.00	7.00	4.2317	2.20716
UES5	82	1.00	7.00	4.0244	2.19413
UES6	80	1.00	7.00	4.7000	2.13707
UES7	82	1.00	7.00	4.7927	2.04117
UES8	82	1.00	7.00	4.8659	2.08322
UES9	82	1.00	8.00	4.7683	2.17334
UES10	82	1.00	7.00	4.8293	1.96767
UES11	82	1.00	7.00	3.9878	2.10522
UES12	82	1.00	7.00	4.8659	1.83762
UES13	82	1.00	7.00	3.9634	2.29570
UES14	81	1.00	7.00	5.2593	1.84240
UESs- core	82	38.00	92.00	64.6829	11.51690

The university environment scale reveals the total mean score and standard deviation. The mean score of the University environment scale is 64.6829. This score presents the overall perception of the university environment as perceived by the International students at an above average level. This score level further explains that the International students have a positive opinion when it comes to university perception. The administrators and faculty can have an enormous effect on the university environment as in the case of SDCA, and the actual experiences the students had: How the university recognizes and includes other cultures can affect the perceptions of friendliness and acceptance of the university? These experiences are governed by the levels to which their own culture and language are recognized and racially balanced into the school program; how involved they become and are motivated to become? and how good educators help them in instruction, guidance, and assessment? Universities are accountable for making an environment where students from ethnically diverse backgrounds will feel valued and will be able to succeed (Madkins & Mitchell, 2000).

Table 1.5 Correlation of the Cultural Congruity Scale and the University Environment Scale

Pearson Cor- relation (r)	Description	p value	Statistical Interpretation
0.097	Low correlation	0.385	Not significant

The correlation of the Cultural Congruity Scale and the University Environment Scale, thus: The p-value of 0.385 ($r = 0.097$) suggests a low, or seemingly negligible correlation which implies that culture is not related to the university environment based from the experiences of the foreign students. These may refer to various issues presented by the respondents who participated in the Focus Group Discussion. For instance, lack of support for the International student athletes compared to the local student athletes, of which there is still relative satisfaction among higher International students, but this may be skewed because of their refusal to be critical with regards to their experience (Bills, 2013; Harman 2003). This is possible since International students are usually capable of employing positive coping strategies and still feel invisible within the university environment (Abdullah and Fotovatian, 2012)

Conclusion and Recommendation

Cultural congruity is not at all correlated with the university environment. However, it is suggested that workshops and programs should be conducted by the college through the Department of Student Affairs Services which will include needs analysis to improve students' management.

International students should be given needs analysis survey and evaluation questionnaires to determine their current needs, challenges and experiences inside the university every semester. Hence, the College management should reevaluate the students' concern such as school fees, human relation skills and building facility needs. As stated by Brown (1991), there are seven possible changes that can be made to improve the retention and recruitment of International students this includes financial aid programs, multicultural university environment, communication and alliances within the community, sensitizing faculty members and academic retention program.

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